

Laser-absorption CO detection at 4.56 μm in the exhaust plume of a full-scale gas turbine burner

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Abstract

We report on the first use of mid-infrared (MIR) laser absorption measurements of CO concentration levels in the exhaust stream of a single full-scale burner at the new Siemens Clean Energy Center (CEC) in Berlin (Germany). A relatively temperature insensitive rotational transition in the fundamental vibrational band of CO was selected to probe the exhaust gas flow from the burner at a pressure of approx. 2 bar. The environment for the laser set-up in the test facility was especially harsh with acoustic noise amplitudes up to 150 dB and temperature variations ($\sim 50^\circ\text{C}$). Optical access for the laser absorption measurements was provided through two sapphire windows (15 mm clear aperture) mounted on a metal flange inserted in the cylindrical exhaust flow duct., which also was equipped with other instrumentation probes (e.g. thermocouples, gas sampling probes). Initial results from the first test campaign are presented.

Introduction

Narrowband tunable laser absorption provides rapid *in situ* and line-of sight integrated measurements of species specific concentrations and temperature in gaseous environments. In this diagnostics small-size optical access is generally sufficient for the transmission of a small diameter laser beam, which is a significant advantage in test facilities, which demand for only minor hardware modifications. In addition, the employed light sources – solid state diode and quantum cascade lasers – are small devices with low electrical power dissipation, can be fiber coupled, and are easily operated remotely. Therefore, these laser-based absorption sensors can be packaged with small footprint for convenient transport and applications in harsh environments with limited space. The usefulness of laser absorption sensors have been demonstrated in a wide variety of combustion applications [1],[2],[3], and a few laser-absorption measurements primarily in the near-infrared have been reported for gas turbine combustor ground test [4].

Here the use of laser absorption to monitor the exhaust from a single full-scale gas turbine burner is investigated. This test environment is extremely hostile with a large acoustic noise background (~ 150 dB) and high ambient temperature ($\sim 50^\circ\text{C}$). This harsh environment provided significant challenges to design a sensor that would survive the testing.

Here we describe an engineering design successfully used during the first measurement campaign with the instrument located next to the exhaust duct of a single burner unit open to the atmosphere. The aim was for all equipment to survive and to demonstrate the proof-of-concept for mid-

infrared laser absorption measurements of CO in the exhaust of the combustor test rig.

Sensor design

The test rig for a single full-scale burner at Siemens new Clean Energy Center (CEC) in Berlin (Germany) is schematically shown in figure 1. The burner exhaust flow from inside the pressure vessel was directed through a cylindrical duct equipped with a pressure drop into a rectangular chimney to the open atmosphere. The CO concentration levels were measured in the exhaust stream directly after the guide wheel, as shown in Figure 1, through wedged sapphire windows (15 mm clear aperture) in two water cooled probes inserted into the flange.

Figure 1: Schematic representation of test rig and access for the laser absorption measurements

The 150 dB acoustic noise is sufficient to damage unprotected electronics and produce strong vibration in the test cell. Human operators were not allowed to enter the test cell during measurements. Thus, after

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Figure 2: Assembly of the sensor (from left to right): top view of the optical emitter bench; cross sectional view of the instrumentation flange; side view of the receiving unit

initial optical alignment sensor operation must be conducted remotely. The first generation sensor used here proved that laser absorption measurements are possible in this harsh environment.

Figure 3 (a) Stainless steel sending window flange with fiber alignment unit; (b) receiving window flange with a small breadboard for receiving unit (sketch).

Figure 2 shows the schematic of the sensor, which consisted of sending and receiving units and controlled by a remote computer via LAN. Single-mode mid-infrared optical fibers (Thorlabs) were used to guide the laser light to a 5-axis-adjustment unit (Newport), which is fixed on the water cooled window probe unit in figure 3(a). A collimator with a fixed focus length (Thorlabs) is screwed onto the fiber output enabling a free space collimated light beam to be transmitted through the entrance window and across the exhaust duct. During warm-up time and while in operation the exhaust duct and its window flange expands and translates several centimetres. Because of the limited clear aperture of the exit window the transmitted light could be blocked. Because of spatial restrictions and the difficulty of adjusting the beam and detector remotely,

for this first test the detector unit was fixed directly on a breadboard, which was firmly connected with the receiver window flange (figure 3(b)). This fixed coupling of both the sending optical fiber output and the receiving unit with their respective window flange has the additional benefit of spatially correlated mechanical movement of both parts during the test phase.

Insulating, sound-proofed box for sending unit

The implementation of the thermal and acoustic insulation is a very important design element for proper functioning of the sensor.

Figure 4: Isolated, sound-proof box: 1 - outer shock-absorbing foam, 2 - water-cooled optical breadboard, 3 - vibration isolator, 4 - room for controllers and fans, 5 - optical breadboard, 6 - room for devices like computer, water cooler, 7 - legs, 8 - sand-filled buckets, 9 - X95 profiles, 10 - item profiles, 11 - wooden plates, 12 - inner shock-absorbing foam

Figure 4 shows the construction of the insulating, sound-proofed container. The entire sending unit, including computer and water thermostat, was

surrounded by a wooden box covered from the outside with shock-absorbing foam. At its top, a second wooden box with shock-absorbing foam on both sides of its walls was fixed on a 900×600 mm optical breadboard, which was mounted on a four-leg rack (SMT, X95-profile). Each of its four legs was immersed in a sand-filled bucket to dampen vibrations from the floor. The optical setup was installed on a water-cooled optical breadboard (450×600 mm, Thorlabs), which rested on four aluminum profiles with passive vibration isolators. Below the water-cooled breadboard two fans provided air circulation within the unit. The remaining space was used to accommodate controllers and power supplies for laser and detectors. A nitrogen purge was supplied to the box to avoid interference due to water absorption along the free-space laser path on the optical breadboard (see Fig. 6 below).

Optical setup sending unit

Figure 5 shows the sketch of the optical setup, while Fig. 6 presents a top view photograph of the sender unit.

Figure 5: Schematical representation of optical setup

A quantum cascade laser (Hamamatsu, 30 mW) emitting near $4.56 \mu\text{m}$ was used to monitor absorption from the R(12) transition (lower state internal energy: 2190.02 cm^{-1}) in the fundamental vibration band of CO. The laser output was free-space coupled into a single-mode InF_3 fiber (Thorlabs) by using a parabolic mirror (Thorlabs). To characterise the laser during the measurements, the light is split into three parts and registered directly (incoming laser power, detector 2 in figure 5), through a reference cell (spectral positioning, detector 1 in figure 5) and through a solid etalon (relative laser frequency calibration, detector 3 in figure 5), respectively. The reference cell is filled with CO probe gas at a low pressure to locate the position of the absorption line. To remotely switch

between laser characterisation and coupling into the launching fiber, a bending mirror can be moved in an out of the beam path by a stepper motor controlled translation stage.

Figure 6: optical setup design on water cooled breadboard.

Optical setup receiving unit

Figure 3 (b) shows the receiving unit schematic. To avoid intensity fluctuations at the detector due to beam-steering effects caused by the high mass flow with turbulence in the turbine exhaust duct, a gold-coated diffuser (Thorlabs) was placed instead of a bending mirror in front of the detector. The detector (Vigo) was in close contact with a water cooled plate to improve heat removal from the Peltier cooler. Additional nitrogen purging was applied for detector cooling.

Sensor application at the CEC

The sensor was assembled and tested at a full scale gas turbine combustor at the Siemens Clean Energy Center (CEC) near Berlin.

Survival test

Before laser measurements were performed an electronics survival test was conducted with a notebook computer inside the insulating, sound-proof box. After a whole test day with a running burner the notebook program had crashed. However after restarting the electronics still worked. We believe the error was caused by overheating, because the breadboard was not water cooled during this test.

A second test was conducted with the water cooled breadboard inside the protecting box for optical setup. All the electronic devices worked without failure even though the ambient temperature was $33 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$.

As mentioned, the aim for the first campaign was the survival of all devices intact and the proof-of-concept demonstration of laser absorption of CO levels in the exhaust flow. After the initial ignition of the combustor, the absorption of CO was detected. The initial raw data are recorded in a relative time domain, which can be converted to the frequency domain (laser frequency scan) via the etalon fringe

pattern recorded simultaneously. As the ambient temperature increased, the thermal radiation from the test rig observed by the detector exceeded the signals from the transmitted laser intensity scattered off the diffusor. Thus, after the initial burner start-up the laser detector was thermally saturated.

For the initial measurements, the laser was current tuned applying a low frequency (100 Hz) sine function, which was modulated by a low amplitude, high frequency (10 kHz) sine function. Before flame ignition the laser was characterized.

Laser characterisation

Figure 7 shows the detected raw signal for an expanded time scale for the reference cell channel without (black line, detector 1 in figure 5) and with (red line, detector 2 in figure 5) addition of 1000 ppm CO in the calibration cell. On this timescale the signal shows a smooth appearance without large variation, which means the sending unit was well enough isolated from the vibration in the test rig. The reference cell here is used to determine the absolute wavelength.

Figure 7: Detected raw signal in the calibration cell in the sending unit for a sinusoidal laser power modulation during operation of the burner test rig

Figure 8: Detected raw signal with CO absorption in exhaust for larger relative time scale

Detection of absorption in exhaust

The detected signal for an extended operation time of the burner is shown in figure 8. It is obvious that on top of the sinusoidal modulation of the laser power erratic signal intensity fluctuations in the range of 5 % of the peak signal due to beam-steering can be observed despite of using a diffusor in front of the detector.

The expanded time scale in Figure 9 shows line absorption features from CO in the exhaust flow. After the first ignition, the pressure in the exhaust duct was low enough (about 2 bar) such that the pressure/induced spectral shift can be neglected. Thus, compared with the spectral line positions recorded in the reference cell (figure 10), we can determine that this absorption was from CO.

Figure 9: Detected raw signal with CO absorption in burner exhaust flow for an expanded relative (with respect to an arbitrary zero point) time scale

Figure 10: Qualitative comparison from 1000 ppm CO in reference cell to the measured CO signal in the burner exhaust duct

To determine CO concentration levels from the measured transmittance values requires real-time temperature and pressure recordings from the exhaust gas flow. These were recorded during data acquisition time spans of the CO sensor. Laser absorption is a line-of-sight measurement and thus will provide spatially averaged information along the

beam path only. A rough estimate of temperature and CO concentration levels would be possible from equilibrium calculations from the known mass flows entering the burner and dilution air in the exhaust channel.

Conclusions and outlook

We presented preliminary real-time CO absorption data provided by a transportable, ruggedized absorption sensor based on a mid-infrared tunable diode laser spectroscopy sensor operated next to the exhaust flow channel of a running single burner from a novel generation gas turbine combustor at the Siemens CEC test site near Berlin. In the first measurement campaign all optical and electronic equipment enclosed in an acoustically insulated and temperature stabilized container survived operation without damage. Cooling power inside the protecting box for transmitter and control electronics was sufficient for smooth operation of the sensor in this harsh environment. Although additional cooling for the receiver (detector) package is needed. From the recorded data streams only small, manageable disturbances were observed caused by mechanical vibrations during burner operation. However further improvements of the sensor design are necessary: The detector and accompanying optics should be protected in a water cooled box, and the band pass filter should preferably be mounted close to the detector to avoid thermal radiation from the surrounding reaching the sensor surface. Beam-steering effects may be further suppressed by, e.g. using an integrating sphere.

During burner operation absorption due to the presence of CO in the facility warm-up phase was observed. However, for a quantitative analysis local temperature and pressure in the optical path must be known. Some improvements of the sensor design can be envisaged:

- Determination of a path-integrated temperature will be performed using diode laser near-infrared absorption from two water lines
- Selection of CO transitions to optimize signal strength while minimizing spectral interference from H₂O and CO₂ in the combustion exhaust.

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